

Metal Complexes Derived from Isobutyric Acid Hydrazide with Some Bivalent Metal Ions

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The preparation and characterisation of some new metal complexes derived from, isobutyric acid hydrazide (IBH), of the types $[M(\text{IBH})_2\text{X}_2]$, $[\text{M}(\text{IBH})_2\text{X}_2(\text{M} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cd}^{\text{II}} \text{ and } \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}; \text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br})$ and $[\text{M}(\text{IBH})_3\text{X}_3\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ ($\text{M} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} \text{ and } \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}$) are reported. Infrared spectral data show that IBH acts as a monodentate ligand and coordinated *via* azomethine group (imidol structure). The stereochemistry of the isolated solid complexes have been discussed with the help of magnetic and spectral (electronic and nmr) measurements.

ACID hydrazides are well known for their antituberculosis activity¹ and their importance as potential sites for transition metal ions. Coordination compounds derived from some aliphatic and aromatic hydrazides with some bivalent metal ions have been reported recently from our laboratory²⁻⁴.

The aim of the present work is to investigate the coordination behaviour of IBH towards bivalent metal ions, to fill up the gap between butyric³ and isovaleric⁴ acid hydrazides, to throw some light on the stereochemistry of the isolated Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, and finally, to find a relation between our findings and what we got in our previous work²⁻⁴.

Experimental

The ligand and its metal complexes were prepared using the same techniques as reported earlier⁴. Molar conductivities were measured on Tacussel CD6NG conductivity bridge using 10^{-3} M dimethylformamide (DMF) at 25°. Magnetic moments were carried out at Oslo University, Norway, using Faraday method. Electronic spectra were recorded in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO), pyridine and nujol mull using a Pye Unicam SP 1800 and a Unicam SP 700C spectrophotometers. Infrared spectra ($4000\text{--}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer at Illinois State University, U.S.A. Pmr spectra were carried out on a Varian EM-360 (60 MHz) spectrometer.

Halides and metal contents were estimated by the standard methods^{5,6}. Carbon and hydrogen contents were estimated in the Microanalytical Unit of Mansoura University.

Results and Discussion

All the isolated solid complexes are crystalline and easily soluble in DMF and DMSO except those of Hg^{II} complexes. Molar conductivities at 25° are found in the range $9\text{--}56\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$ indicating their non-electrolytic nature⁷. Analytical results and some physical properties are listed in Table 1.

The infrared spectra of some aliphatic and aromatic acid hydrazides have been discussed by Mashima^{8,9} and Jensen¹⁰. The most important bands in the spectrum of the free ligand as well as the bonding sites, in the spectra of the metal complexes, have been determined by a careful comparison of the ir spectra of IBH and its metal complexes in the light of the data reported earlier⁸⁻¹⁰. Our earlier work²⁻⁴ and that of Ahmed *et al.*¹¹ have also been taken in our consideration.

The ir spectrum of IBH shows that it exists mainly in the keto form and it shows λ_{CO} at 1685 cm^{-1} as a shoulder and no bands above 3330 cm^{-1} expected for the enol form. The observation of the carbonyl band as a shoulder and the NH bands at lower wavenumbers than those reported¹² for the free NH bands, in the spectrum of the ligand, suggests the presence of hydrogen bonding. Also, the existence of two broad bands at ~ 2000 and 1850 cm^{-1} due respectively, to N-H...O stretching and bending vibrations¹³ confirms the presence of intra-molecular hydrogen bonding which is probably formed between the carbonyl oxygen and NH_2 groups as shown in structure 1.

The ir spectra of the isolated solid complexes show that the ligand coordinates *via* the imidol

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TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES AND MOLAR CONDUCTIVITIES OF IBH COMPLEXES

Compd.	M. p. °C	Colour	Analysis % :		Found / (Calcd.)		Molar conductance in DMF, Λ_m $\Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$
			C	H	M	X	
Zn(IBH)Cl ₂	243	white	19.9 (20.1)	4.2 (4.2)	23.3 (23.6)	29.6 (29.7)	13
Zn(IBH) ₂ Cl ₂	182	white	27.9 (28.2)	5.8 (5.9)	19.0 (19.2)	20.7 (20.8)	11
Zn(IBH) ₃ Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O	202	white	31.9 (31.9)	6.9 (7.0)	14.1 (14.2)	15.2 (15.4)	9
Cd(IBH)Cl ₂	300	white	16.7 (16.8)	3.3 (3.5)	39.1 (39.4)	24.6 (24.8)	24
Cd(IBH) ₂ Cl ₂	165	white	24.7 (24.8)	5.1 (5.2)	29.2 (29.0)	18.5 (18.4)	39
Cd(IBH) ₃ Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O	206	white	28.2 (28.4)	6.1 (6.3)	22.0 (22.1)	13.6 (14.0)	21
Hg(IBH)Cl ₂	> 360	grey	12.8 (12.9)	2.6 (2.7)	—	18.8 (19.0)	—
Hg(IBH) ₂ Cl ₂	> 360	grey	20.2 (20.2)	4.2 (4.2)	—	14.8 (14.9)	—
Co(IBH)Cl ₂	70	blue	20.7 (20.7)	4.2 (4.3)	25.3 (25.4)	30.5 (30.6)	40
Co(IBH) ₂ Cl ₂	110	violet	28.6 (28.8)	6.0 (6.0)	17.7 (17.6)	21.2 (21.2)	28
Co(IBH) ₃ Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O	158	pink	31.7 (31.7)	7.0 (7.1)	12.9 (13.0)	15.5 (15.6)	33
Ni(IBH)Cl ₂	121	green	20.6 (20.7)	4.3 (4.3)	25.3 (25.3)	30.4 (30.6)	36
Ni(IBH) ₂ Cl ₂	142	green	28.7 (28.8)	6.0 (6.0)	17.5 (17.6)	20.5 (21.2)	—
Ni(IBH) ₃ Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O	154	blue	31.4 (31.7)	7.0 (7.1)	12.8 (12.9)	15.4 (15.6)	—
Ni(IBH)Br ₂	300	green	14.8 (15.0)	3.1 (3.1)	18.3 (18.3)	49.8 (49.8)	36
Ni(IBH) ₂ Br ₂	139	green	22.6 (22.7)	4.7 (4.8)	13.7 (13.9)	37.7 (37.8)	—
Ni(IBH) ₃ Br ₂ ·H ₂ O	252	violet	26.5 (26.5)	5.9 (5.9)	10.8 (10.8)	29.4 (29.4)	—
Cu(IBH)Cl ₂	143	green	20.3 (20.3)	4.2 (4.3)	26.8 (26.9)	29.9 (30.0)	37
Cu(IBH) ₂ Cl ₂	118	green	28.1 (28.4)	5.7 (5.9)	18.6 (18.8)	20.8 (20.9)	56
Cu(IBH) ₃ Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O	135	green	31.2 (31.4)	6.8 (7.0)	13.8 (13.8)	15.2 (15.4)	21
Cu(IBH)Br ₂	136	green	14.6 (14.8)	2.9 (3.1)	19.5 (19.5)	48.7 (49.1)	38
Cu(IBH) ₂ Br ₂	148	green	22.3 (22.5)	4.6 (4.7)	14.7 (14.9)	37.4 (37.4)	37
Cu(IBH) ₃ Br ₂ ·H ₂ O	170	green	26.2 (26.3)	5.8 (5.9)	11.5 (11.6)	29.0 (29.2)	19

structure. The following evidences support the coordination through the azomethine nitrogen. The disappearance of both $\nu_{C=O}$ (1683 cm^{-1}) and ν_{NH} (990 cm^{-1}) bands in all metal complexes with the simultaneous appearance of new bands at ~ 1595 , 1035 and 940 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu(C=N)$, $\nu_{as}(C=O)$ and $\nu_s(C=O)$ vibrations, respectively. The appearance of a broad band around 3440 cm^{-1} (irrespective of whether or not the solid complexes contain water) which we attribute to ν_{OH} vibration. The presence of a free OH group in the ligand comes from the pmr spectra of the diamagnetic complexes in d_6 -DMSO. For example, in solutions of $[Zn(IBH)_2Cl_2]$ and $[Cd(IBH)_2Cl_2]$, the OH proton signals at 14.25 and 14.15 ppm respectively, downfield from TMS disappears upon addition of D_2O . The small positive shift of the band at 1090 cm^{-1} due to ν_{N-N}^{14} in the spectrum of the ligand suggests that IBH coordinates *via* one of the nitrogen atoms. The

bands at 1635, 1260 and 1133 cm^{-1} attributed to $\beta(NH_2)$ and $\delta(NH_2)$ remain unchanged suggesting that the NH_2 group is not taking part in coordination.

All the tris-ligand complexes exhibit a molecule of water in the coordination sphere (irrespective of the metal ion used). The existence of a coordinated water in the solid complexes is confirmed by the following evidences. The bands at ~ 1610 , ~ 770 and ~ 570 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu(H_2O)$, $Qr(H_2O)$ and $Qw(H_2O)$ vibrations¹⁸, respectively. The water molecule is not removed when the complex is dried

in vacuo over P_2O_5 . Finally, the observation of a signal at 4.85 ppm downfield TMS, in the nmr spectra of the diamagnetic tris-ligand complexes, in d_6 -DMSO disappears upon deuteration.

Magnetic and spectral measurement : The values of magnetic moments and the electronic spectra of the solid complexes in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO), pyridine and nujol mull are shown in Table 2. The electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes (Cl and Br) are very similar

both ν_1 and ν_2 in the complexes increases on going from chloro- to bromo-complexes, indicating that the tetragonality of the chloro- are less than those of the bromo-complexes as expected from the position of the halogen in the spectrochemical series¹⁹. The electronic spectra and the magnetic data of the Co^{II} complexes show both tetrahedral and octahedral complexes with isobutyric acid hydrazide. The blue complex, $[Co(IBH)Cl_3]$, has a magnetic moment in the range normally found for tetrahedral Co^{II} complexes and exhibits the ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow$

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL AND MAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF IBH COMPLEXES

Compd.	Solvent	Magnetic moment μ_{eff} B.M.	Electronic spectra (in $cm^{-1} \times 10^3$)		D_q	B	β	$\frac{\nu_2}{\nu_1}$
			Ligand field bands					
$Ni(IBH)Cl_2$	DMSO	3.14	9.1, 12.2(sh), 14.7, 17.2(sh), 24.1		910	767	0.74	1.61
$Ni(IBH)_2Cl_2$	DMSO	3.26	9.3, 12.1(sh), 15.1, 17.2(sh), 25.1		930	813	0.78	1.62
$Ni(IBH)_3Cl_2 \cdot H_2O$	DMSO	3.18	9.8, 10.1, 12.0(sh), 15.9, 16.3, 17.5(sh), 25.2		980	780	0.75	1.62
$Ni(IBH)Cl_2$	Py	3.14	9.9, 12.4(sh), 16.0, 17.4(sh), 25.6		990	793	0.76	1.62
$Ni(IBH)_2Cl_2$	Py	3.26	9.9, 12.7(sh), 16.1, 17.7(sh), 26.0		990	827	0.79	1.63
$Ni(IBH)_3Cl_2 \cdot H_2O$	Py	3.18	10.1, 10.6, 12.7(sh), 16.3, 17.1(sh), 17.5, 26.2		1010	813	0.78	1.61
$Ni(IBH)Cl_2$	Nujol	3.14	8.9, 12.2(sh), 14.5, 17.1(sh), 24.4		890	813	0.78	1.63
$Ni(IBH)_2Cl_2$	Nujol	3.26	9.6, 12.3(sh), 15.9, 17.1(sh), 25.0		960	807	0.77	1.66
$Ni(IBH)_3Cl_2 \cdot H_2O$	Nujol	3.18	10.1, 11.2, 12.2(sh), 16.4, 16.9, 17.4(sh), 25.6		1010	780	0.75	1.62
$Ni(IBH)Br_2$	DMSO	2.78	9.2, 12.2(sh), 14.9, 17.6(sh), 24.3		920	773	0.74	1.62
$Ni(IBH)_2Br_2$	DMSO	3.26	9.9, 12.2(sh), 15.9, 17.2(sh), 25.9		990	807	0.77	1.61
$Ni(IBH)_3Br_2 \cdot H_2O$	DMSO	3.12	10.0, 10.7, 12.4(sh), 16.2, 16.4, 17.2(sh), 26.1		1000	820	0.79	1.62
$Ni(IBH)Br_2$	Py	2.78	10.1, 12.2(sh), 16.4, 17.1(sh), 25.6		1010	780	0.75	1.62
$Ni(IBH)_2Br_2$	Py	3.26	10.3, 12.5(sh), 16.7, 17.5(sh), 26.2		1030	800	0.77	1.62
$Ni(IBH)_3Br_2 \cdot H_2O$	Py	3.12	10.5, 11.7, 12.5(sh), 16.9, 17.3(sh), 17.7, 26.5		1050	793	0.76	1.61
$Ni(IBH)Br_2$	Nujol	2.78	9.2, 12.7(sh), 14.9, 17.2(sh), 24.5		920	787	0.76	1.62
$Ni(IBH)_2Br_2$	Nujol	3.26	9.6, 12.3(sh), 15.6, 17.3(sh), 25.1		960	793	0.76	1.62
$Ni(IBH)_3Br_2 \cdot H_2O$	Nujol	3.12	10.2, 11.2, 12.5(sh), 16.7, 17.4(sh), 17.7, 25.8		1020	793	0.76	1.64
$Co(IBH)Cl_2$	Nujol	4.36	3.21, 5.6, 15.1		321	738	0.76	—
$Co(IBH)_2Cl_2$	Nujol	5.14	8.5, 16.7, 18.2, 19.7		955.5	817	0.84	—
$Co(IBH)_3Cl_2 \cdot H_2O$	Nujol	5.20	8.6, 16.8, 18.5, 20.0		965	830	0.99	—
$Cu(IBH)Cl_2$	Nujol	1.74	13.1					
$Cu(IBH)_2Cl_2$	Nujol	1.80	12.8					
$Cu(IBH)_3Cl_2 \cdot H_2O$	Nujol	2.06	12.5					

and have magnetic moments clearly characterising them as octahedral. Three bands are observed in the regions 8900-10500, 14500-16900 and 24100-26500 cm^{-1} assigned to the ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P), vibrations, respectively, in the spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes. On the basis of the band positions, magnetic moments and the calculated values of ν_2/ν_1 , $10D_q$, B and β , an octahedral geometry¹⁶ is presumed for all the Ni^{II} complexes. The mono- and bis-ligand complexes are most probably polymeric with halogen bridges, and they show ir bands in the regions 235-245 and 240-260 cm^{-1} due to ν_{Ni-Cl} ¹⁷ and ν_{Ni-N} ¹⁸ vibrations, respectively. Transitions to spin singlet levels are observed in the regions 12000-12700 (${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$) and 17200-17800 cm^{-1} (${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$). The electronic transitions from the ${}^3A_{2g}$ to the ${}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3T_{1g}$ and ${}^3T_{1g}$ (P) terms increase in energy in going from the mono- to the tris-ligand complexes, indicating that in the environment of the nickel atoms the number of nitrogen ligand increases. No splitting of the bands due to tetragonality is observed for the mono- and bis-complexes but the tris-complexes show a splitting in both ν_1 and ν_2 . Also, the energy of

4T_1 (F) and ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1$ (P) transitions in the 5600 and 15100 cm^{-1} regions as expected. Also, the calculated values of $10D_q$, B and β are in a good agreement with those reported in the literature^{20,21}. The electronic spectra and magnetic moments of the violet and pink complexes are typical to those reported for octahedral Co^{II} complexes²⁰; the 8500-8600 cm^{-1} band being ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$, the band around 16700 cm^{-1} being the ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and that in the 19700-20000 cm^{-1} being the ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}$ (P) transition. The pink complex, $[Co(IBH)_3Cl_2 \cdot H_2O]$, shows a broad band centered at 3460 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra which is not present in the violet complex, $[Co(IBH)_3Cl_2]$, due to a coordinated water and is not removed by drying *in vacuo*. All these observations may suggest that the pink complex may have a monomeric structure with a coordinated water two halide ions and three unidentate IBH ligands.

The spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes are very similar to the spectra of tetragonal Cu^{II} complexes and the magnetic moments confirm that no reduction to Cu^I or anomalous magnetic behaviour is occurring.

On comparing the results of IBH with those of butyric acid² (BuH) and isovaleric acid hydrazides⁴ (IVH), we found that IBH behaves toward bivalent metal ions more or less in the same way like IVH than BuH, i.e. IBH coordinates via the imidol structure as IVH and not through the NH₂ group like BuH. Also, the tendency of coordination as well as the coordination number is decreased in going from butyric acid to isovaleric acid hydrazides, in the order BuH>IBH>IVH, due to the steric hindrance. Finally, the stability constant for the complexes (Co, Ni, Cu), calculated from the molar and continuous variation methods²²⁻²⁴, is decreased in the opposite way, i.e., IVH>IBH>BuH.

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